

On Photochemical Reaction between Bromine and Tartaric Acid in Aqueous Solutions. Part III.

The Mechanism of the Reaction.

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Any mechanism that may be postulated for this photochemical reaction should account for the following experimental observations recorded in Part II (*previous paper*).

1. The induction period diminishes with increase in the frequency and intensity of incident light.

2. The induction period increases as the initial concentration of tartaric acid increases.

3. The induction period diminishes as the initial concentration of bromine is increased.

4. The induction period increases very considerably if hydrobromic acid is added to the reaction mixture previous to exposure to light.

5. In a reaction mixture containing bromine, tartaric acid and sodium hydrogen tartrate, the induction period increases as the initial pH of the solution diminishes.

6. The unimolecular velocity constant with respect to bromine, diminishes as the initial concentration of bromine increases.

7. The same constant increases as the concentration of tartaric acid increases.

8. The value of this constant increases very considerably if a fraction of the tartaric acid in the reaction mixture is replaced by an equivalent amount of sodium hydrogen tartrate.

9. The value of this constant diminishes considerably if hydrobromic acid is added to the reaction mixture before exposure to light.

10. As the reaction proceeds, the unimolecular constant with respect to bromine continues to diminish, this diminution being more marked in weaker solutions of tartaric acid than in the more concentrated solutions. In a mixture of bromine with excess of tartaric acid and sodium hydrogen tartrate the values of the unimolecular constant are fairly concordant among themselves.

11. The velocity of the reaction increases very rapidly as the frequency and the intensity of light increases. In fact for blue light,

in a mixture of bromine with excess of tartaric acid and sodium hydrogen tartrate, the values of the unimolecular constant vary approximately as the square root of light intensity.

12. A quantum of light absorbed by the system is responsible for the transformation of a large number of bromine molecules into hydrobromic acid.

It appears that all these complex features of the reaction between bromine and tartaric acid in aqueous solution can be explained if we assume the following mechanism of reaction:—

The first stage in the reaction is obviously the activation of bromine molecules by the absorption of light. The experiments of Bodenstein and Berthoud, and the various experiments on photobromination carried out in this laboratory indicate that it is the atom of bromine that is responsible for bringing about photochemical reaction. This hypothesis has been corroborated by the work of Frank who has shown that a quantum of wave-lengths shorter than the band limit of bromine, *i.e.*, 5200\AA , decomposes the bromine molecule into a normal atom and a metastable atom (Faraday Soc. Discussion on "Photo-chemical Reactions in Liquids and Gases", p. 540). We assume necessarily the following transformation:—

We have seen, however, that green, yellow and even red light is in a position to bring about photobromination, though the efficiency of light diminishes very rapidly as the wave-length increases. It is well known that the absorption for moist bromine vapour begins at 6100\AA , and for bromine solution it begins somewhat earlier. But quantum of this frequency is not in a position to decompose bromine molecules, which are only pushed up to a certain stage of activation. These activated molecules may, in some cases, acquire fresh energy by collision with other molecules in the system, and undergo dissociation into atoms. This possibility of the transformation of the kinetic energy of collision into the heat of dissociation of bromine is the greater, the greater the internal energy of preliminary activation of the bromine molecule by the absorption of a quantum of radiation. It is well known that this possibility of conversion of energy of collision into internal energy of active molecules is the real reason for the absence of a photochemical threshold which we

meet with in simple photo-electric phenomena. It therefore follows that absorption of light where γ is greater than 5200\AA may lead to the dissociation of bromine molecules into atoms, but the fraction of excited molecules so dissociated into atoms rapidly diminishes as the wave-length increases. We have thus a qualitative explanation of the observed fact that the efficiency of light for photobromination diminishes rapidly as the wave-length increases beyond 5200\AA .

We should next trace the various phases through which this bromine atom passes. In the first place two atoms of bromine may combine to regenerate a molecule of bromine thus

The rate of re-formation of bromine molecule is therefore

$$K_2[\text{Br}]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Secondly, an atom of bromine is deactivated by collision with molecules of oxygen present in the system.

This theory is very familiar to all investigators who have studied photochemical reactions in which chlorine or bromine is involved. It has always been found that the presence of oxygen very considerably retards the velocity of reaction and the current explanation is that whenever an atom of chlorine or bromine collides with a molecule of oxygen, it becomes practically inert for purposes of photo-halogenation.

The rate of deactivation of bromine atom is, from (3), given by

$$K_3[\text{Br}]^2[\text{O}_2] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where $[\text{O}_2]$ represents the concentration of oxygen molecules in the system. The presence of oxygen can be traced to two sources.

(1) Oxygen remaining dissolved in water used for these experiments.

(2) Oxygen obtained from the dark reaction,

The velocity of this dark reaction, as has been noted already is very small and falls off with time, and perhaps in a closed vessel, we are dealing with reversible reaction of the type,

Since the velocity of reactions indicated in (5) is very small, equilibrium concentration of oxygen, once attained, will not be perceptibly disturbed if the concentration of bromine rapidly diminishes or the concentration of hydrobromic acid quickly increases in the course of another rapid side reaction.

The concentration of oxygen in the reaction mixture may thus be considered constant during the processes of photobromination which in our experiments were completed in about three hours.

This equilibrium condition of oxygen existing in the solution previous to the exposure to light is from (5) obviously proportional to the square of the initial concentration of bromine;

$$\text{or } [\text{O}_2] = K_4 [\text{Br}_2]^2 \text{ initial} \quad (6)$$

Thirdly, in the initial stage of photobromination, the active bromine atoms may be used up in destroying a class of substances which act as photo-inhibitors and which are almost invariably present in reacting systems. This inhibition effect is very pronounced in the photochemical reaction between hydrogen and chlorine. Thus Weigert (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 131, 271) recommends the following precaution in the preparation of Bunsen—Roscoe actinometer:—

“Zunächst wurde nach jeder Neufüllung des Aktinometers das Gas-gemisch mit einer kleinen Glühlampe, die mit 0·6 Amp. und 6 Volt an einer Akkumulatorenbatterie Konstant brannte, induziert. Wenn das Gas einige Tage und Nächte ununterbrochen durch das system hindurchgeleitet war, war die Induktionsperiode schnell überwunden, und man erhielt immer wider Indexbewegungen derselben Grössenordnung von etwa 2 cm./Min bei einem Abstand der Prüflampe von 1 m.”

The rate of destruction of these photo-inhibitors will therefore be proportional to the concentration of bromine, and the intensity of incident radiation. Here too, the frequency of light exerts a great effect, for the higher the frequency, the greater is the possibility of

the decomposition of the bromine molecules into active atoms, and hence, the quicker is the rate of destruction of inhibitors.

It appears that hydroxyl ions have also great influence on the rate of destruction of these inhibitors by bromine in presence of light. Chlorine and bromine in an aqueous solution containing (OH') ions give the hypochlorite and the hypobromite respectively. In the case of sodium hypochlorite solution, it has been definitely shown by W. C. McLewis, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 237) that the hypochlorite decomposes in light in alkaline or neutral solution into sodium chloride and atomic oxygen. The rate of production of atomic oxygen is proportional to the concentration of hypochlorite ion and the intensity of blue and violet radiation. The active rays are in the blue, violet and ultraviolet regions. In the dark, however, the decomposition takes place only very slowly. Similarly to chlorine, we may assume that bromine produces hypobromite by reaction with hydroxyl ions, and this hypobromite ion in presence of blue and violet light decomposes into bromide ion and an atom of oxygen. The photo-inhibitors present in the reacting system is very quickly destroyed by the atom of oxygen and transformed into harmless substances. On this basis, is readily intelligible the influence of the following factors on the diminution of induction period :—

- (1) Increase in the intensity of illumination.
- (2) Increase in the frequency of radiation.
- (3) Increase in concentration of bromine.
- (4) Increase in the concentration of OH' ion.

Lastly, the active bromine atoms are responsible for the photo-bromination of tartaric acid. We have seen that one quantum of absorbed radiation can transform more than 50 bromine molecules. This is possible, if we have a chain mechanism in which the bromine atom used up in a reaction, is regenerated in a subsequent reaction. Such chain reactions are, however, bound to be hypothetical unless in any instance, the intermediate compounds postulated in such mechanism can be proved to exist. It is preferable to imagine that in the bromination of tartaric acid which is an exothermal reaction, the bromine atoms are not actually used up and regenerated in alternate chains, but that the bromination can only take place in a three-body collision, between a bromine atom, a bromine molecule, and a bitartrate ion : the bromine atom may be considered to be a catalyst which remains unaltered during this transformation.

The rate of photo-bromination will then be given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = K[\text{Br}][\text{Br}_2][\text{HT}'] \quad \dots (7)$$

We have postulated above that it is the HT' which takes part in photobromination and not the molecule of tartaric acid, There are two reasons for this assumption—

(a) If the reaction mechanism as given by (7) were modified so as to substitute a molecule of tartaric acid in place of (HT') ion, the reaction, for a constant concentration of bromine atom after a stationary state has been reached, would have been bimolecular. The bimolecular velocity constants were however not found concordant among themselves.

(b) It has been mentioned before that if the total initial concentration of tartrate radical be kept constant in a reaction mixture but the ratio of HT' to tartaric acid molecule increased by taking suitable proportions of sodium hydrogen tartrate and tartaric acid, then the reaction velocity increases very considerably. This observation is thus a definite evidence in favour of the assumption that HT' ion and not the molecule of tartaric acid is the reactive substance. Equation (7) is capable of quantitative verification from the experimental data recorded in the previous paper.

The concentration of free [Br] after a stationary state has been reached and the photo-inhibitors destroyed, can be obtained from the equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Br}]}{dt} &= K_1 I - K_2 [\text{Br}]^2 - K_3 [\text{Br}]^2 [\text{O}_2] = 0 \\ \text{or } [\text{Br}] &= \sqrt{\frac{K_1 I}{K_2 + K_3 [\text{O}_2]}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{K_1 I}{K_2 + K_3 K_4 [\text{Br}_2]_{\text{initial}}}} \quad \dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

where I is the intensity of incident light and $K_1 I$, therefore, represents the rate at which the free [Br] is generated. This is true only under the condition that the value of I absorbed does not vary during the progress of the reaction. In a paper by Ghosh and Purkayastha, (*This Journal*, 1927 **4**, 420,) this point has been thoroughly discussed and it has been shown that for blue light the variation in the amount of light absorbed during the progress of the

reaction when the final bromine concentration drops to a quarter of its initial value is negligible. The rate of disappearance of bromine is equivalent to the rate of formation of HBr and we have

$$\frac{d[\text{HBr}]}{dt}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{dx}{dt} = K(a-x) \cdot [\text{HT}'] \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{K_3 I}{K_2 + K_3 K_4 [\text{Br}_2 \text{ initial}]^2}} \right\} \dots \quad (9)$$

The term within { } may be considered constant during the progress of a reaction, and we have

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K(a-x)[\text{HT}'] \cdot K_5 \dots \quad (10)$$

The concentration of HT' in a solution of tartaric acid is given by the Ostwald equation,

$$[\text{H}^+] [\text{HT}'] = K_6 [\text{tartaric acid}]$$

where K_6 is the first dissociation constant of tartaric acid. Now C , the concentration of tartaric acid may be taken as constant during a reaction because (1) K_6 is very small, *i.e.*, practically the whole of the acid may be considered as undissociated and (2) the concentration of tartaric acid in our experiments was always far in excess of that of bromine, the ratio of molecular concentration of tartaric acid to bromine being never less than 8.

Now at any stage of the reaction when the concentration of hydrobromic acid is x , x' , the conc. of HT' ion is given by

$$(x+x')(x') = K_6 C$$

$$\text{or, } x' = \frac{-x + \sqrt{x^2 + 4K_6 C}}{2}$$

The velocity of reaction is therefore given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \cdot K_5 (a-x) \left\{ \frac{-x + \sqrt{x^2 + 4K_6 C}}{2} \right\} \dots \quad (11)$$

Where a is the initial concentration of bromine in gram equivalents per litre, x is the amount of bromine in gram equivalents that disappeared at any time t , C is the molecular concentration of tartaric acid in gram molecule per litre, K_s is Ostwald's constant for the first dissociation of tartaric acid when concentration is expressed in gram molecule per litre (0.00099).

The integration of the equation (11) is rather complicated but it can be accomplished and we obtain the relation

$$2(K_s C). K.K_s t = \text{Constant} - (x + \sqrt{x^2 + 4K_s C}) \\ - (a + \sqrt{a^2 + 4K_s C}) C \log (a - x) - a \log e (x + \sqrt{x^2 + 4K_s C}) \\ + (\sqrt{a^2 + 4K_s C} \log e (\sqrt{a^2 + 4K_s C}) \sqrt{x^2 + 4K_s C}) \\ + ax + 4K_s C) \quad \dots (12)$$

The expression to the left will in the following table be designated by A.

In Table I, are given some experimental data which go to show that the constants obtained from equation (12) agree very well among themselves: t is expressed in minutes.

Table I (*vide* Table VIII—Part II).

Filters of copper sulphate and methyl violet solutions were used as recommended by Plotnikow to obtain light of wave-lengths between 4780—4100Å (Schwerpunkt—4480Å).

Intensity—3.8 Hefners-at-100 cm.

Initial conc. of tartaric acid—M/7.5. Initial conc. of bromine N/30.

Temp.—33.6°.

t	$a-x$	x	A	$K.K_s$	Unimolecular velocity constant with respect to $[Br_2]$.
0	.03425	0	$2.3 \times .0402$	—	—
20	.02675	.0075	$2.3 \times .0430$	1.21	.0054
45	.02190	.0125	$2.3 \times .0460$	1.20	.0048
101	.01500	.0191	$2.3 \times .0584$	1.20	.0035
191	.00875	.0255	$2.3 \times .0663$	1.21	.0081

Tables II-VI give some typical data for light of wave-length $526\text{-}458\mu\mu$ (Schwerpunkt $488\cdot5\mu\mu$) and it is at once evident that the constants obtained from equation (12) agree very well amongst themselves.

TABLE II (*vide* TABLE XXII, PART II).

Intensity of incident light ($488\cdot5\mu\mu$)—11·5 Hefners-at-100 cm.
Tartaric acid—M/3. Bromine N/30. Temp.— $33\cdot3^\circ$.

t	$a-x$	x	A	KK_s	Unimolecular constant.
0	·03225	0	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot02910$	—	—
5	·02675	·00550	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot03234$	2·23	·0162
15	·01975	·01250	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot03837$	2·13	·0142
26	·01550	·01675	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04422$	2·01	·0122
39	·01187	·02086	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot05218$	2·04	·0116
56	·00787	·02438	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot0682$	2·08	·0109

TABLE III.

Intensity of incident light ($488\cdot5\mu\mu$)—11·5 Hefners-at-100 cm.
Tartaric acid—M/7·5. Bromine—N/30. Temp.— $33\cdot5^\circ$.

t	$a-x$	x	A	KK_s	Unimolecular constant.
0	·03400	0	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04093$	—	—
25	·02075	·01325	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04762$	2·31	·0086
41	·01700	·01700	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot05160$	2·24	·0073
72	·01200	·02200	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot05912$	2·19	·0063
106	·00800	·02600	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot06952$	2·33	·0059

TABLE IV (*vide* TABLE XII, PART II).

Intensity of incident light ($488\cdot5\mu\mu$)—6 Hefners-at-100 cm
Tartaric acid—M/15. Bromine—N/30. Temp.— $33\cdot5^\circ$.

t	$a-x$	x	A	KK_s	Unimolecular constant.
0	·03275	0	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04218$	—	—
10	·029375	·003375	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04292$	1·36	·0047
30	·024625	·008125	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04479$	1·53	·0041
60	·02075	·01200	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot04634$	1·38	·0033
90	·01700	·01575	$2\cdot3 \times \cdot05000$	1·53	·0032

TABLE V (*vide* TABLE IX, PART II).

Intensity of incident light ($488.5\mu\mu$)—6 Hefners-at-100 cm.
Tartaric acid—M/3. Bromine—N/30. Temp.—33.5°.

t	$a-x$	x	A	KK_2	Unimolecular constant.
0	.031975	0	$2.3 \times .02799$	—	—
6	.02800	.0338	$2.3 \times .02996$	—	—
16	.023875	.0085	$2.3 \times .03373$	1.60	.0110
46	.01975	.01763	$2.3 \times .04630$	1.48	.0081
76	.00800	.02338	$2.3 \times .05993$	1.52	.0080

TABLE VI.

Intensity of incident light ($488.5\mu\mu$)—6 Hefners-at-100 cm.
Tartaric acid—M/3. Bromine—N/20. Temp.—33.5°.

t	$a-x$	x	A	KK_2	Unimolecular constant.
0	.04550	0	$2.3 \times .04542$	—	—
10	.03925	.00625	$2.3 \times .04785$.842	.00610
25	.03300	.01250	$2.3 \times .05150$.842	.00564
45	.02675	.01875	$2.3 \times .05662$.856	.00513

It will be seen that the value of the constants KK_2 in the fifth vertical column agree very well among themselves, whereas the unimolecular velocity constants with respect to bromine rapidly diminish as the reaction proceeds.

Table VII contains the values of constants KK_2 for blue light with Schwerpunkt at 488.5 \AA .

Light intensity Hefners-at-100 cm.	Initial conc. of tartaric acid.	Initial conc. of bromine.	KK_2
11.5*	M/7.5	N/30	2.25
11.5	M/3	N/30	2.10
6	M/15	N/30	1.45
6	M/3	N/30	1.55
6	M/3	N/20	.86

* The value of the intensity is only approximate.

It will be seen that when the initial concentration of bromine and the intensity of the incident light are the same, the product of the constants KK_3 is, as is to be expected, independent of the concentration of tartaric acid.

Also for the same concentration of bromine, the ratio of the velocity constants ($2.15/1.5 = 1.43$) is equal to the ratio of the square root of the corresponding light intensities ($\sqrt{11.5/6} = 1.40$). This is exactly what is demanded by equation (9) for the velocity of the reaction.

With increase in the initial concentration of bromine, the product KK_3 diminishes at the same intensity of incident light. This is also to be expected as the value of K_3 is dependent on the initial concentration of bromine, being, as is indicated before, given by the expression,

$$K_3 = \sqrt{\frac{K_1 I}{K_2 K_3 K_4 [\text{Br}_2]_{\text{initial}}^2}}$$

In fact if K_3 is small compared with $K_1 K_4 [\text{Br}_2]_{\text{initial}}^2$, we should expect that K_3 should be inversely proportional to the initial concentration of bromine, which is approximately the case as will be seen from Table VII.

When the concentration of the bitartrate ion approximately remains constant during the course of the reaction, the progress of the reaction is given by the simple equation,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K(a-x).C.K_3 \quad \dots (13)$$

and the equation is that of a monomolecular reaction, where

$$K' = K.C.K_3 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

The value of K' is proportional (i) to the original concentration of the bitartrate ion and (ii) to the square root of the intensity of illumination. These experimental conditions are realised when to the

reaction mixture containing bromine and tartaric acid, sufficient sodium hydrogen tartrate is added. It will be seen from Tables XVI and XVIII in Part II that the unimolecular velocity constants for large concentrations of tartaric acid containing sufficient sodium hydrogen tartrate are fairly concordant among themselves, and these constants for the same initial concentration of bromine are proportional to the square root of the intensity of the incident light.

Our best thanks are due to our friend Prof. S. N. Bose for his help in the evaluation of the integral in equation (12).

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Received March 14, 1928.